

GUIDEBOOK

Sharing field notes

Part of the project

'Beyond Personal Data: RDNL training on hard-to-share data for SSH early-career researchers'

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Licence

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution licence (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
CV	Controlled vocabulary
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (see https://gdpr.eu/)
NWO	Dutch Research Council (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek)
RDNL	Research Data Netherlands (Dutch national coalition of research-supporting organisations, see https://researchdata.nl/)
ROR	Research Organization Registry (https://ror.org/)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TDCC	Thematic Digital Competence Centre

Taking archaeological field notes in Jordan. Photo: Pascal Flohr.

About this guide¹

Recent years have seen a surge in efforts to make academic research more open as well as FAIR - findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable - for humans as well as machines (Wilkinson et al., 2016). While practices to increase the FAIRness of data are increasingly common, some of these can be harder to adopt in disciplines that rely on qualitative research methods such as the social sciences and humanities. In light of promoting FAIRness in these domains, this guide tackles one specific methodological tool in qualitative research: field notes.

Field notes are written data used to capture observations and research context. They form the 'raw' or primary data and/or essential contextualisation in different types of qualitative research in disciplines like archaeology, sociology, and cultural anthropology. They can vary from handwritten, completely unstructured text in a notebook, to manually or digitally filled out forms. What they have in common is that they form the, mostly descriptive, original observations or the context of the research. As such, sharing field notes is important for research integrity and the verification of results. However, field notes are often not shared for various reasons and there is very little

practical advice on how to share them.² This guide addresses this gap by giving an overview of best practices for sharing and publishing field notes and practical guidelines for doing so.

The guide includes sections on:

1. An introduction to field notes (what are their characteristics and how are they used)
2. When to share or not share field notes
3. Legal and ethical prerequisites for sharing field notes
4. How to prepare field notes for publication

Who is this guide for?

The target audiences of this guide are researchers producing field notes and research data professionals like data stewards advising these researchers. The focus of this guide is on field notes from the social sciences and humanities (SSH) although the recommendations in this guide may also be applicable to other fields. Field notes are commonly used in SSH disciplines such as archaeology, anthropology or ethnography, sociology, linguistics, law, and qualitative health research (and beyond the SSH in disciplines like ecology, biology, and geology).

¹ To learn more about the project, see Thorpe et al. (2025).

² For guidance on, among other things, how to produce field notes and what they should contain, see for example Philippi and Lauderdale (2018), Sakel and Everett (2012), Mulhall (2003), Walford (2009), and contributions in Sanjek (1990).

Note on terminology

In this guide we use terminology that is common for data professionals, but not always outside of this field. In order to avoid any misunderstanding or ambiguity, we would like to clarify our wording.³

- 1. Data sharing:** we use the word 'sharing' in the broad sense of 'giving access to others', including sharing data directly with other researchers, archiving with (later) sharing in mind, and publishing field notes for others to use and reuse. Nonetheless, because the bottleneck, or challenge, lies mostly with the last type of sharing, we mostly focus on the open or partly restricted publication of field notes.
- 2. Open data:** data that are publicly available and published for everyone to see, for example in a research data repository, institutional repository, or as supplementary information. Ideally the data are available with an open licence that allows reuse such as a CC BY licence.
- 3. Data publication:** the process of making your research data available on a publication platform, so that others can see, investigate, and ideally reuse them. The platform is preferably a research data repository, but it can also be an institutional repository or you can publish the data in an academic journal as supplementary materials with an article.
- 4. Data archiving:** the long-term storage of your research data and documentation. The aim is preservation and reproducibility, but not necessarily reuse by others.⁴
- 5. FAIR data:** the FAIR principles intend to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of your data (Wilkinson et al., 2016; GO FAIR Foundation, n.d.). FAIR data is not the same thing as open data. Data that cannot be shared openly, can be made FAIR by openly providing metadata, like information about the location and access conditions.
- 6. Metadata:** metadata is 'data about the data'. In the context of data management, metadata is a structured form of documentation. Standardised and detailed documentation is vital to explain the meaning and content of your data to your colleagues, peers, as well as your publisher, editor, or peer reviewer. Careful documentation is part of good research practice and it makes data publishable, discoverable, citable, and reusable. It is important to have metadata and documentation for your field notes, even when you are not planning on openly sharing them.

³ For a further introduction to these concepts, see also the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (CESSDA, 2017-2022) and the video series 'Open Science Tips', available at <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL-vTxWFyVBpHsi5Rv8XNB502yuXnwj877>.

⁴ Certified data archives, such as the DANS Data Stations or UK Data Service, allow for archiving data with different access conditions: open (anyone can access it), restricted (accessible only under specific conditions), or closed (not accessible under any conditions). In the case of very sensitive data, an in-house archiving solution may be a better choice than an external one or a cloud solution.

1. Field notes, the basics

In this guide we focus on field notes⁵ compiled as part of research. To understand if, and if so how, we can share research field notes, it is useful to look into their characteristics and uses within research.

1.1 Characteristics of research field notes

Researcher field notes:

- are often **compiled directly** during fieldwork⁶, or briefly afterwards
- are generally made to **describe observations** made during fieldwork and the researcher's reflections thereupon
- are meant as **data** to support a research hypothesis
- are normally **qualitative**
- take the form of **textual or descriptive** records, when relevant including sketches or drawings

(Emerson et al., 2011; Jovanović, 2022a)

Field notes can be accompanied by (audio)visual forms of data, such as photographs, drawings, measured plans, or voice memos. Because sketches and drawings tend to be included in the same medium (e.g. a notebook) and in the

same workflow, we class them here as part of field notes (Fig. 1-2). They may, however, be digitised or digitally treated differently (e.g. as images). Field notes can also be accompanied by quantitative data like measurements; however, when there are only quantitative data we are probably dealing with a different type of notes, like lab notes or experiment sheets, which have a different set of challenges than qualitative field notes.

Figure 1: Overview of field notes and accompanying information recording tools.

5 Other commonly used terms include field diary, field book, daynotes, or scratch notes (see Jovanović, 2022a; Sanjek, 1990). The term field report is also used, but refers more to a summary of the fieldwork done and is often written (based on field notes) afterwards.

6 We are not delving into the question of what the 'field' is in fieldwork or field notes; rather we assume that if you call it 'fieldwork', your related notes will be 'field notes'.

Field notes can be created in different ways:

- **Analogue:** on paper, like in a notebook
 - This can be **digitised**, for example through scanning or typing out the text
- Directly digital ('**born-digital**')

How field notes were created, affects how they can be shared (see further section 4).

Field notes vary from completely **unstructured** 'scribblings' (Fig. 2); **semi-structured**, using free, descriptive text but according to a certain structure or plan; to **structured**. (Fig. 3) Structured notes may still contain free text, but are done according to a certain predefined structure using standard answers in a controlled vocabulary. An example is the archaeological field form (Fig. 3).

Figure 2:
Example of unstructured
handwritten field notes with a
sketch, Malinowski 1884-1942,
Yale Library Collections (public).

a:

Page 7

Area: B Square: A9 Locus Number: 26

Progress of Excavation: Work started on Sunday morning 27th of January by cleaning and removing debris which had been gathered from the previous season of excavation 1983. our work continues in revealing Loc. 26 which represents a stone wall

Locus Description: A group of stones formed together a semi-circular wall runs towards west side and it may continue beneath the bank which separate Sq. B.A.9 from B.A.8 (width of this bank is 1. m). This wall was removed later. (A sketch and photo was taken). The stone wall was resting on dark grey soil which goes down to a depth of 35cm.

Location in Square: This stone wall located at south west corner of this Sq.

b:

PAGE 2

KNS 031

Feature Form(s) - Certainty - Arrangement - Shape - Number

Rock-cut depression 2x, -1x circular
-1x irregular

Feature Interpretation(s) - Certainty - Number

- Askn
- ?

Site Function(s): Hydrological -Dep. + Agr./Past. -Med. and/or Domestic -low

c:

EAMENA Disturbance/Threat Record Sheet

*If there is more than one disturbance at the site, assign a number to each one to link Disturbance Cause/Category/Effects/Date(s)

Site:		Date:		Initials:		
Condition:	<input type="checkbox"/> Good	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor	<input type="checkbox"/> Very Bad	<input type="checkbox"/> Destroyed	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Disturbance Extent:	<input type="checkbox"/> 1-10%	<input type="checkbox"/> 11-30%	<input type="checkbox"/> 31-60%	<input type="checkbox"/> 61-90%	<input type="checkbox"/> 91-100%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown <input type="checkbox"/> No Visible/known						
Disturbance Cause(s):						
<input type="checkbox"/> No Visible/known	<input type="checkbox"/> Explosion/Heavy Weaponry	<input type="checkbox"/> Maintenance/Prevent.	<input type="checkbox"/> Stationary Vehicle			
<input type="checkbox"/> Animals/Pest Infestation	<input type="checkbox"/> Fire	<input type="checkbox"/> Mine/Quarry (Open Pit)	<input type="checkbox"/> Structural Robbing			
<input type="checkbox"/> Clearance (Bulldozing)	<input type="checkbox"/> Flooding	<input type="checkbox"/> Mine/Quarry (Surface)	<input type="checkbox"/> Temp./Humidity Change			
<input type="checkbox"/> Clearance (Hand)	<input type="checkbox"/> Graffiti	<input type="checkbox"/> Mine/Quarry (Sub-Surf)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tunnelling			
<input type="checkbox"/> Clearance (Unclassified)	<input type="checkbox"/> Grazing/Animal Movement	<input type="checkbox"/> Mine/Quarry (Unclass.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Veg./Crops/Trees			
<input type="checkbox"/> Conservation	<input type="checkbox"/> Gunfire/Light Weaponry	<input type="checkbox"/> Occupation/Cont. Use	<input type="checkbox"/> Volcanic Eruption			
<input type="checkbox"/> Construction	<input type="checkbox"/> Inundation	<input type="checkbox"/> Ploughing	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Action			
<input type="checkbox"/> Demolition	<input type="checkbox"/> Irrigation (Centre Pivot)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pollution	<input type="checkbox"/> Wind Action			
<input type="checkbox"/> Drilling	<input type="checkbox"/> Irrigation (Channels)	<input type="checkbox"/> Precipitation	<input type="checkbox"/> Unknown			
<input type="checkbox"/> Dumping	<input type="checkbox"/> Irrigation (Unclassified)	<input type="checkbox"/> Railway	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):			
<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation (Machinery)	<input type="checkbox"/> Land/Rock Slide	<input type="checkbox"/> Reconstruction				
<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation (Hand)	<input type="checkbox"/> Landmines	<input type="checkbox"/> Road/Track				
<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation (Unclass.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Landscaping	<input type="checkbox"/> Seismic Activity				

Figure 3:

- a) Part of a semi-structured archaeological field form filled in using free text (Van der Kooij et al., 2009);
- b) part of a (semi-)structured archaeological field form, in which terms from a (not shown) controlled vocabulary list are used (Flohr, unpublished);
- c) part of a structured form (EAMENA project, 2018).

1.2 Uses of field notes

The main uses of field notes are as **primary data** for answering a research question and for **contextualisation** of (other) research data. In addition, they can be used for other purposes: for example, a researcher can use them to reflect on their fieldwork methods and interpretation (Emerson et al., 2011; Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018). Because field notes contain rich and important contextual information of certain phenomena, sociogeographic areas, and/or communities, they can also be useful for **reuse** by others, for example in a metasynthesis, or when they revisit the same or a comparable area (Lutkehaus, 1990; Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018; Halbertsma, 2019) (see also section 2.1).

Depending on the aim of taking the field notes and the discipline, field notes can be made with having in mind the wider research community or at least researchers in the same field from the start, but they are often intended for personal use by the researcher (Emerson et al., 2011; Jovanović, 2022a).⁷ While especially older field notes are now available in the public domain (e.g. Malinowski, 1884-1942; Moynihan, 1957-1963), they were normally not originally written with the general public in mind, which often impacts the accessibility, legibility, and ethical context of this type of data (Fig. 2) (see also section 3.2).

1.2.1 Field notes as primary data

Field notes are used as primary data when

observations are written down as field notes, to be used as the basis (or one of the sources) for further analyses.⁸ Field notes in this case essentially form one of the methodological tools for recording information (documentation), either as the only tool or together with for example interview recordings (Jovanović, 2022a).

The use of field notes as primary data is important in ethnographic research. In cultural anthropology, for example, a researcher may stay with, or visit, a community and write down their conversations and descriptions of people and their environment as completely as possible during their stay (Sanjek, 1990; Emerson et al., 2011).

Malinowski's early 20th century notes are a famous example (Fig. 2; Malinowski 1884-1942) (see Álvarez Roldán, 2002) (for another example, see case study 1 / Verheijen and van der Geest, 2020). Field notes are also an important part of the primary data in archaeological fieldwork, especially in academic archaeology (for example Akkermans (2014), Van der Kooij et al. (2009b), Meijer (2025); Fig. 3), and beyond the SSH domain in disciplines like ecology (e.g. Moynihan, 1957-1963).

7 See Phillippi and Lauderdale (2018) on why the latter is not recommended.

8 Field notes can be 'raw' data too. With raw data we mean the original, unaltered, unprocessed data, for example handwritten field notes. Raw data can serve as primary data directly or be processed before using. When processed, for example digitised, these data would still serve as primary data, although they would no longer be considered raw data.

Another example of field notes as primary data comes from refugee studies. As it is not possible to make recordings (see also section 3), taking field notes is the main way of recording information for the researcher:

“He talked about migrants without fear or hatred. He says that he sometimes drives families, that some of them are really nice and that he doesn’t charge them much more than others. He says that the transport of migrants does not count as smuggling, because he is not allowed to ask anyone for their ID, what they plan to do or where they are going next.”

Jovanović
2022b

1.2.2 Field notes for contextualisation

Field notes enable researchers to add non-verbal, non-textual, context, like the social and temporal context, so that the full depth of the study context can be understood (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018).

This can concern field notes about:

- The study context: for example, what is the study area like geographically, and what resources are available to the people living there, or to the researcher? (see box and Fig. 4)
- The interview setting: what was the room like, who were present, how did the participant come across?
- The interview itself, like non-verbal cues, which is especially useful when only audio is recorded. This non-verbal context can be added to the interview transcripts to better understand the meaning of the participant (see box and Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018).

In the following example, field notes are used to note information about the study context:

“Walked up Brdwy N. into Cuban Grocery. Too busy to establish contact with workers. There is a Cuban Rest -Nice- next to it (Liberia) and a Spanish Restaurant across the street.”

George

1977

Figure 4: George, 1977, Chicago Ethnic Arts Project (Library of Congress, Public Domain)

This next example by Philippi and Lauderdale (2018) shows how non-verbal context can have added value in a transcript:

*“When I found out that I was HIV+, I didn’t acknowledge it for six months. I didn’t tell anyone. **[long pause while looking at his feet]** Not even my wife....”*

Philippi and Lauderdale

2018: p. 386, our emphasis

2. To share or not to share field notes?

2.1 Why share field notes?

It can be very valuable for field notes to be shared for both research integrity and reuse. When the notes are part of a, or even form the complete, research dataset, they are needed to understand the analyses and conclusions. Also the context of fieldwork or interviews can be essential to understand, reproduce, and reuse the research. Making field notes available is, then, important for transparency, so that others can understand and verify what the conclusions are based on and suggest alternative interpretations (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018; Verheijen and van der Geest, 2020; Verburg, Braukmann and Mahabier, 2023).

Making field notes available for reuse allows others to use the notes to answer their research questions, and enhances visibility of the research (Lutkehaus, 1990; Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018; Verburg, Braukmann and Mahabier, 2023). Data collection through fieldwork is time-consuming and, moreover, certain types of fieldwork projects cannot be repeated in the same way: archaeological excavation, for example, destroys the archaeological context essential for interpretation of the results, endangered languages are disappearing, ethnography is recording changing societies, and so on. In some cases, the field notes themselves can even be more useful for other researchers than related publications. Moreover, fieldwork often results in substantial amounts of field notes that contain rich and descriptive data, which renders it unlikely that one researcher or

research team will completely study them and publish about all aspects.

2.2 Why not?

On the other hand, it is simply not always possible to publish or otherwise share field notes, for example if they contain personal data or other sensitive information and it is too much work or not completely possible to de-identify the notes. Given the descriptive and contextualised nature of field notes, such and other legal aspects as well as ethical considerations often constitute a reason not to share field notes (see section 3). In addition, due to the sheer volume of field notes, they may only really be useful to others when a lot of work is put in, like digitising, structuring, and/or annotating the notes. The time to put in this work may not be available, or there may not be a good balance between putting in this work and what you (or others) get out of it. For ethnographic field notes, for example, it is often argued that they are not useful or understandable without context (see also Emerson et al., 2011), while annotating the notes would take a lot of time (but see Verheijen (2013a, b, c) for an example where this has been skillfully and usefully done). Unfortunately the publication of data, like field notes, is not yet valued equally to publishing a journal paper or book, although work is being done on increasing recognition for such outputs (VSNU et al., 2020). These practical considerations often restrict researchers in their ability to share field notes.

2.3 How to decide?

In essence, the decision on whether or not to share field notes comes down to asking oneself: **Is it useful** (for other researchers, beyond the research field) **and not harmful** (to the participants/observed people, to yourself/the people who took the notes), as well as **feasible** (in terms of workload)?

One should consider:

- 1) Do the field notes contain or form the raw or primary data, i.e. the main data on which your conclusions are based? If so they should be shared as openly as possible, and at least the metadata should be published openly and the rest archived (if open sharing is not possible).⁹
- 2) Do the field notes include contextual information essential for understanding or replicating the research? In this case, they should especially be shared as openly as possible, with at least the metadata published openly and the rest archived.
- 3) If the field notes do not contain primary data or essential contextual information, are the field notes meaningful to others, also considering the time required for potential necessary processing?
- 4) Are the legal and ethical preconditions for sharing the field notes (openly) met? How to assess this is further discussed in section 3.

⁹ See the introduction section for definitions of data archiving, publishing, sharing, open and FAIR data, and metadata.

* See also the flow chart by Verburg et al., 2023. ** Explanation in figure caption and in the main text.

*** If needed destroy files with personal / sensitive data.

Figure 5: Decision tree on deciding whether to (openly) share field notes or not. Anonymisation: the data can no longer be used to identify a person, all directly or indirectly identifiable data are irreversibly removed. Pseudonymisation: the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific person without the use of additional information; this is reversible if access to additional information, like a separate list of participants, is gained or if certain information is combined (CESSDA Training Team, 2017-2022).

Case study 1a: Sharing anthropological field notes

Based on the 26 May 2025 workshop presentation by Janneke Verheijen as well as her publications (Verheijen and van der Geest 2020; Verheijen 2013a, b, c; Verheijen in Flohr et al. 2025), summarised by the guide authors.

Janneke Verheijen lived for a year in a village in Malawi to conduct research on women's sexual relationship choices and the risks of HIV in these relationships. She did this work together with a research assistant from the capital of Malawi, Getrude. It was challenging work, for seven days a week for a full year.

Since the topic of their research was sensitive, especially in the cultural context and because the lead researcher was from another country and therefore an outsider, the researchers were unable to directly ask questions about the topic. Instead, they had to embed themselves within the community and take very detailed notes about their observations and conversations with women in the village. Janneke said: *"So by the end of the year, I had a lot of written material, beautifully rich – but totally chaotic, because [there were no] neatly structured interviews, most of it [were] descriptions of daily life, of the conversations at the waterpump and at our house while knitting. From my perspective and from Gertrude's."*

Back in the Netherlands, Janneke typed out (digitised) and coded around 600 (!) pages of notes using ATLAS.ti (qualitative data analysis software). By digitally coding her field notes, she could click on the relevant codes and get

all the excerpts relating to a particular topic. She then grouped these excerpts further, identifying patterns in the data, and finally drawing conclusions.

Janneke had not initially planned to share the notes themselves, but she was struck by how rich and beautiful they were and this made her think about the value of sharing them with others. She also realized the importance of others being able to read her field notes to assess the claims she made in her research. *"If I would leave them in, and open up the whole dataset ... these beautiful stories would not be lost, would remain accessible and part of the final product, and anyone interested could get more background information and could [assess] the strength of my conclusions and come to different ones maybe."*

Moreover, she wanted to give her participants a voice: *"These are among THE most unheard people on earth, because no one is willing to go there, to spend some time there, to not only do quick interviews and leave as quickly as possible again: the very people that anthropologists want to give a voice. Providing insight into these stories would be a way to do that..."*

The question was, though, if she, as the researcher, was entitled to expose all these stories. Could it cause harm to the participants? Janneke had permission to do the research and to share the insights, emphasizing the right not to participate. It was also made clear that everything that the women told her or

the research assistant could be included. However, it was not clear if this permission included sharing the field notes.

She returned to the site of her research to ask for consent to openly share the field notes. Permission was granted in part because the field notes mainly consisted of 'public' knowledge and gossip, which was already known to people in the village, and therefore unlikely to cause harm to the participants. Janneke shared the (carefully pseudonymised) notes as part of her thesis (see section 4, case study 1b, for the way she shared the notes; see also section 3).

3. Prerequisites / requirements for sharing field notes

To decide on how openly your field notes can be shared, it is necessary to take into account several legal and ethical aspects.

3.1 Legal considerations

Here it is foremost important to assess if personal data are included in the field notes. If you are based within the EU or in the UK, or otherwise deal with data from EU or UK citizens and residents, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies.¹⁰ Personal data concern any information that can be used to identify a living person. If your field notes contain personal data, you will need to check if informed consent was acquired to share the data and in what form the data are allowed to be shared.¹¹ Good practice here is to also ask yourself if the participants indeed understood the informed consent completely: were they aware, for example, that offhand remarks written down as notes could also be included as part of the data? Subsequently, is it sufficient for the data to be pseudonymised (identifiable information is removed, but it is possible to reconstruct the identity using a key) or do they need to be fully anonymised (and is this possible at all)? If no sufficient informed consent was acquired from the participants and/or if it is not possible to sufficiently pseudonymise or anonymise the notes, in that case only publish the metadata

and archive the field notes themselves (Fig. 5). If data is completely anonymous, then it is no longer considered personal data and the GDPR no longer applies. Informed consent would not legally be needed to share this data but there would be ethical considerations. Moreover, it is very difficult to fully anonymise datasets while still rendering them useful and it is a very time-consuming process (see Campbell et al., 2023).

Resources on personal data

To learn more about how to get proper informed consent, and how to pseudonymise or anonymise your field notes, see the following resources (you can find the full references in the bibliography):

- Verburg et al. (2023). 'Making Qualitative Data Reusable'
- RDNL online course 'GDPR for Data Support' (RDNL, n.d.)
- CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide, chapter 5, 'Anonymisation' section (CESSDA Training Team, 2017-2022)
- LCRDM guide 'Pseudonymization and key files' (Kleef et al., 2019)
- Campbell et al. (2023). 'Open-Science guidance for qualitative research'
- Truan et al. (2024). 'Interviews going open!'
- If you are in an organisation where there are privacy officers, you can ask them for advice

¹⁰ For more information, see <https://gdpr.eu/>; for the UK see <https://www.gov.uk/data-protection>.

¹¹ There are also other legal grounds for processing personal data (<https://gdpr.eu/article-6-how-to-process-personal-data-legally/>), but for research purposes informed consent is generally the legal ground which is applicable.

There may also be other legal restrictions — make sure you familiarise yourself with local laws, regulations, and required permissions. When working abroad, you can ask for help from local collaborators and partner universities/ organisations as well as from within your own institution. For example, permission for fieldwork but also publication of results (i.e. including field notes) may be required from a governmental authority (like a Department of Antiquities or similar for archaeological fieldwork) or other, local body, and there may be certain preconditions, like publication in their journal or the submission of the data or a report about the data to them first. In another example, certain data may not be allowed to be shared at all, such as the location of heritage sites in some countries.

3.2 Ethical considerations

This is a very broad topic, and we recommend you also look at our guide on the ethics of sharing fieldwork data in general (Lushaj et al., in prep.). Here we can only briefly mention the most relevant aspects for sharing field notes.

3.2.1 Do No Harm

Overall, the main principle is to Do No Harm (International Red Cross, 1965). However, it is not easy to apply this — what is harmful and how to know? And how to decide, for example, between collective benefit and potential individual harm? Is it fine to work with a regime that does not care about human rights, if your fieldwork can be beneficial to local communities in the country? How to know if something that is not harmful now, is not going to be so in future, for example because of a regime change or changing public sentiments? It is not possible to give one-size-fits-all answers here, and there are

no clear answers to these dilemmas to start with. What you can do, is to use additional guidance from the field of humanitarian aid and applied ethics (e.g. Timmins and Thomas, 2024). You can also draw from the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (see 3.2.2).

3.2.2 Be inclusive and involve the local community

The second main principle is to be inclusive. Ensure that all contributors are included in the decision-making. What is also important is to consult with the local community, also beyond direct participants and those producing the notes or the data the notes are based on. If you are working on the lands of or with people from an Indigenous Community, the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance are relevant. These CARE principles are briefly summarised in the ‘CARE principles’ box. For a more extensive discussion as to how to apply these to your research and how to get help in doing this, see our Guide 3 (Lushaj et al., in prep.) and for example Jennings et al. (2023).

It is important here not to make the assumption that consulting more people will lead to more restricted data sharing. In some cases it may even be the other way around, where a researcher might assume data access needs to be restricted, but where participants may actually want their voices to be heard. While as the researcher you are the one responsible for ensuring that people understand the possible consequences of sharing their data, people also have a right for their data to be shared if they wish to do so (see also Verheijen and Van der Geest (2020); and the Authority to Control principle of the CARE principles for Indigenous Data Governance (Jennings et al., 2023)).

Case study 2: Ethnographic field notes from Dutch food forests - rural sociology

By Anna Roodhof

To answer the main research question of my PhD in rural sociology, namely: 'how do food forestry farmers maintain and continue their livelihood?' I engaged in prolonged ethnographic fieldwork at four Dutch food forests. For a full year, I visited each food forest once per month to work alongside the farmers. The main aim was to get a grasp of economic activities that took place in and around the food forests in different seasons. While I complemented this participant observation with semi-structured interviews, the majority of data collected was in the form of field notes.

The type of data recorded in these field notes ranged from personal information about the research participants, their political views, encounters with the Dutch tax authority, experiences with other food forest farmers, financial calculations of product sales and revenue, and other personal experiences shared with me that were relevant for understanding the context of each case study. Much of this information will not be used for publication, but has shaped the interpretation of the data and the research conclusions as a consequence. While I obtained informed consent from each research participant, I did establish relationships of trust with them, and some of the 'data' in my field notes were disclosed to me in confidence. This, as such, complicates the sharing of these field notes.

Prior to starting, as well as during, the

fieldwork, I was aware of the fact that these field notes needed to be digitally stored at a minimum, and would ideally be shared in some shape or form. In previous research efforts, and per the norm in the field of rural sociology, I had not made raw data available in open access. In my field it is common practice to simply include a statement that this data is available upon request. While this does technically require researchers to organise this data accordingly, in practice such requests rarely occur. As food forestry is somewhat of a trendy topic at the moment, I realised that this 'norm' might not suffice for my work — as for previous publications I had received multiple requests already. As such, I kept up the digitalisation process of field notes so as to facilitate the potential sharing of field notes.

However, in the process of pseudonymising field notes, I realized that this effort was futile. The field notes contain extensive information that reveals who participants are even when names are changed. Specifically, the sociogeographic descriptions of landscapes in which the case studies were located are essential to understanding the economic makeup of respective food forests. As all of my case studies also have an online presence to some degree, ranging from formal websites to personal weblogs, they can easily be identified based on the contents of field notes.

All in all, bearing in mind the CARE principles, I decided to properly organise my field notes and create the metadata necessary for reuse thereof. However, I decided not to publish these notes at an open access database and stick to the 'conventional' approach of making them available upon request.

CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance

The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance give guidance on how to include Indigenous Peoples in data governance (Carroll et al., 2020) and move “from consultative to values-based relationships” (Jennings et al., 2023). We summarise Jennings et al. (2023) here with these short descriptions:

(C) Collective benefit

The research (and sharing of the field notes) should be of value to the Indigenous community.

(A) Authority to Control

The Indigenous community has the authority to control data about their lands, members, and traditions; the data should be provided for free and in a usable format, and approval for sharing of the field notes should be obtained.

(R) Responsibility

“Community-researcher partnerships must be driven by community needs and aspirations, and inclusive of Indigenous values, worldviews, and methodologies.” (Jennings et al., 2023).

(E) Ethics

The research should be guided by ethical obligations, taking into account differing ethics and worldviews when deciding about the use, reuse, and sharing of data.

The CARE principles complement open and FAIR data efforts to increase research integrity, reproducibility, and transparency by aiming to make data as open as possible and at least FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), which are often done from a data stewardship, researcher, or university perspective. If you work with local communities who are not an Indigenous community as such, you can take inspiration from the CARE principles (CARE-informed).”

Figure 6: The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, redrawn from Jennings et al. 2023, who adapted it from Carroll et al. 2020 (CC BY).

3.2.3 Who decides?

Decision-making and authorship

Consider who should be involved in the decision on whether (and how) the field notes are shared or not, also beyond the legally required informed consent from any participants. Ideally, plan ahead and ensure that this is all clear to everyone involved from before data collection and thus field note compilation. It is important to create clear expectations for all parties early on in the research, and to make sure all parties are familiar with the institution's or generally accepted codes of conduct (Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, 2018; ALLEA, 2023). Some practical guidelines for field notes sharing are:

1. Include all contributors in the decision-making, and these are not necessarily only the people that contributed to writing down the field notes (or other data collection, see case study 3). Authorship and data sharing agreements should be set up at the start, which is also a good moment to get any necessary permissions.
2. There should be space to revise agreements as the project evolves, such as when new researchers are added to the project or research plans change. In practice, prolonged fieldwork is often dynamic. All members of the research team need to be aware of the changes and involved in the decision-making process.
3. Be mindful of the power dynamics within the research team and with research subjects and how this impacts inclusivity and decisions about research. For example, junior researchers are often left out of decision-making. If you are a junior researcher, pointing out accepted codes of conduct may help, as may pointing out guidelines of journals a project lead may want to publish in (e.g. Holcombe, 2021).

All in all, it is important to be mindful of expectations and agreements, and explicitly discuss and reflect on data sharing agreements throughout the research process. A Data Management Plan, required by many funders and institutions, is a good place to put this information and it can help start the discussion if needed.

3.2.4 Who is responsible?

It is also good to discuss who will be responsible for the work (i.e. for the efforts of sharing the field notes) in practice and who will be responsible in the long term. During the research project, it will likely be the main researcher on a (sub-part of a) project, i.e. the first author of the paper/book or the PhD candidate writing the thesis, the main person collecting and analysing the data, who will also be responsible for ensuring the data is managed well, and is reproducible and sharable.

It is often assumed that in the long term, this same person remains responsible for the data and for deciding who it can be shared with. However, this is not necessarily the case. In many countries, including the Netherlands, if you work for an employer, the work produced is in principle 'owned by' or rather the responsibility of, this employer (see LCRDM (2024) and for example the Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations (Leiden University, 2025)). There is also the increasing realisation by Indigenous Peoples and local communities that the data may — at least ethically— be theirs, together with increasing technical knowledge of these groups enabling them to take the responsibility for the data. Again, it is good to discuss such things at the start, and to take into account

all authors, collaborators, as well as people from local communities you may work with.

Case study 3: Linguistic field notes and their authorship

Based on the Sharing Field Notes workshop presentation by Martine Bruil, see Bruil in Flohr et al. 2025.

Martine Bruil, University Lecturer at the Leiden University Centre for Linguistics, uses field notes in her collaborative language documentation projects in Ecuador. She both reuses earlier notes of others and creates her own field notes. The reuse of others' notes is useful for understanding the circumstances of previous work done on the same language, as well as to have data of an earlier stage of the language.

The notes she and her team make themselves are handwritten notes taken during, and in addition to, recordings and transcriptions, elicitation sessions, and sessions in which the materials are edited. They are not currently shared, and to do so the notes would first have to be made legible.

Moreover, since the language documentation is done in collaboration with local communities, i.e. the speakers of the language, this is an important aspect for the authorship and decision-making about sharing the field notes and other research outputs.

This is formalised through authorship agreements, where:

- The speakers are authors of their data
- The linguistic researcher is author of their analysis
- The speakers can be co-authors of the analysis depending on their input
- The speakers are the authors of the language materials
- The linguist(s) may be co-authors of the language materials

Because the field notes contain data, making them publicly available would need to be discussed with, and agreed upon by, the collaborators.

4. How to share field notes?

Up until now, this guide has discussed points of consideration when deciding on sharing field notes. Once you have decided to share field notes, the next step is more practical: How will you share your field notes? The main question to ask yourself here is: How can the notes be most useful? Different disciplines have different conventions about how to take field notes and what to put in them, and within disciplines different people take notes in different ways (Walford, 2009). Because of the variety of forms and content, the way to share them, and the processing that may be required, also differs.

4.1 Plan ahead

It helps to plan ahead: What sort of field notes will you be taking, in what form, for what purpose, and for whom? When taking the field notes, ensure that you have your audience in mind and keep it professional. Even if you do not share them publicly, they are part of your research data, to be archived for a certain amount of time, and someone at some point might read them (Philippi and Lauderdale, 2018). When the field notes contain personal data or otherwise sensitive information, it is essential to plan ahead to get informed consent, to collect the least amount of personal information possible, to use pseudonyms from the start, and to keep the notes safe.

4.2 What to include?

Field notes are part of the research data, and therefore can, and should, be shared as part of the whole dataset. To decide what to include:

- Take into account legal and ethical restraints (see section 3)
 - For example, only share de-identified notes
- Assess what is needed for understanding and reusing the research
- Keep in mind that not everything may be relevant, but also that it can be difficult to predict what might be relevant in the future

One decision to make is whether to share the original version and/or a processed or curated version of the field notes. Here it is important to ask: Will someone else be able to make sense of the data? In some cases (a scan of or digitised version of) the original notes may be understandable and insightful on their own, or at least in combination with the other data in the dataset, such as in the case of archaeological field forms, extensive ethnographic descriptions, or verbatim conversations. In other cases, the notes may not be understandable without additional information, such as shorthand notes. Walford (2009), for example, cites ethnographer Paul Conolly as saying:

"... So what I wrote in these little pocket books were just shorthand notes of quick incidents written down, broadly, a couple of sentences really... I would then use these to write up more detailed notes in the evening...."

(Walford, 2009: 120, "detained" replaced by "detailed" here).

In this case, the notes in the pocket books (i.e. the raw data) would probably not be worth sharing (unless someone would be studying the ethnographic process itself), but the detailed notes written in the evening (the primary data) would be, because they contain all the information captured in the initial pocket book notes. The pocket book notes by themselves would be incomprehensible, but sharing both would make it clear how the researcher has edited and (perhaps inadvertently) expanded on their field notes when they were writing them up.

In many cases, it will be useful or even necessary to keep the original version archived

somewhere, even if it is not openly shared.

This original version forms part of your research data and depending on the restrictions you or others may be able to reuse it in later research. For example, if removing precise coordinates or detailed location information from archaeological field notes to deter potential looters, it is essential to have this information archived for the long term somewhere so that it can be accessed and shared with at least other archaeologists (for research purposes or to protect the archaeological remains). On the other hand, people’s original names instead of pseudonyms may not add anything to the research and keeping them only risks the data being re-identified.

	No restrictions: field notes can be openly shared	Some restrictions: redacted field notes can be openly shared	Restrictions: field notes cannot be openly shared
Publish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original raw and primary field notes • Any processed field notes • Documentation and metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processed, redacted field notes • Documentation and metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation and metadata
Archive		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original raw and primary field notes • Documentation and metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original raw and primary field notes • Any processed field notes • Documentation and metadata

Figure 7: Simplified guide to help decide what to archive and what to publish (see the ‘note on terminology’ at the start of the guide). Note that the distinction between raw and processed field notes is not always the same between disciplines and between researchers within disciplines. If raw field notes are ‘jottings’ and completely integrated into typed out field notes, it may, for example, not be necessary to publish or even archive the jottings — this is best decided by you as the researcher. ‘Redacted’ can be de-identified or otherwise redacted.

In some cases, field notes of observations (i.e. field notes in their raw or primary form) may not be understandable to others without added context (i.e. in ethnographic studies, Emerson et al., 2011: 93). We argue here that it is good practice to nonetheless publish or at least archive them, to show the research process, decisions made, and the selection made for publication. Moreover, adding sufficient documentation and metadata will help others to understand the notes better. If there is time, extensive annotations, coding, or linking specific notes to specific parts of a publication can help even more (see Verheijen, 2013a, b, c).

4.2.1 Include documentation and metadata

In order for someone else to use field notes, it is important to include documentation and metadata. Metadata is data about data that explains the provenance of the data, which can help a researcher understand the dataset, and gives credit to everyone involved in the project. Metadata is even more important when field notes do not contain extensive annotations.

You can think of documentation and metadata as made up of three different levels:

- For the research project as a whole (be it a larger project or your personal one-person project)
- For the specific dataset (e.g. this bunch of field notes, or all data, such as photos and transcripts, from a single project)
- For the data level (i.e. the actual text of the field notes)

Table 1 sets out what sort of documentation and metadata should be included for these different levels. You can see generic metadata fields that are applicable to projects and datasets of any discipline. In addition, there are

Example of a dataset including field notes

The Deir 'Alla project shared their digitised archaeological field notes and photographs openly through the DANS Data Station Archaeology (van der Kooij et al., 2009a, b, c).

The three datasets include:

- A deposition letter, explaining the context, contents, naming conventions, etc.
- The scanned “paper sheets” containing the **field notes and sketches**, field drawings, plans, section drawings, field reports, and other notes, forms, and lists, as PDFs
- Scanned photograph negatives and slides as JPGs

Figure 8: Screenshot of a small part of the dataset (Van der Kooij et al., 2009b).

metadata fields that are specific to (groups of) disciplines. For example, ‘cultural period’ is relevant for field notes of archaeological and historical research, but not for field notes about current societies. To determine what to use for your project, you can think of what information would help someone else to understand, find, and reuse your field notes and other data.

Metadata fields and other documentation

Project level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title • Authors • Contributors • Institution(s) (ROR, ror.org) • Dates • Funders • Grant number <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related projects • Publications • Keywords (CV) • Description • Subject (CV) <p>See Dublin Core (https://www.dublincore.org/resources/metadata-basics/)</p>
Dataset level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title • Authors / Contributors / Creators: who wrote the field notes and who gave input otherwise? • Community affiliation: Which local or Indigenous community/ies was/were involved? • Dates: date of collection, dates of processing, date of publication (+ were the notes written directly or later?) • Keywords (CV) • Language(s) (CV) • Description • What does it contain? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type(s) of field notes (jottings, written out but primary, processed, etc.) • List of files with file formats • Methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection method (CV plus description) • Sources and theories used • Compiled following any structure? • Tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Written by hand, directly on a computer? Hard- and software used</i> • Intended audience during writing • Anything affecting the author's 'stance' (Emerson et al., 2011) • Processing methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Are all notes included or a selection (and why)? Was any de-identification done and if so how?</i> • <i>Was any coding done and if so how?</i> • Anything else that is relevant to know about your method in your discipline for others to understand and reusing the field notes • Geographical coverage / provenance (CV) • Access: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where are the field notes? • How to get access? • Rights: Conditions & licences (CV) • Who is responsible for giving access? • How to cite? • Traditional Knowledge & Biocultural labels / Disclosure notices (see Local Contexts Hub at localcontexts.org) • Discipline-specific documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>E.g. for archaeology: cultural period / dating, heritage/site type (e.g. the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus, https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/).¹²</i> • <i>E.g. for social sciences: sampling procedure, collection mode (see DDI, https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/).¹³</i> • Related publications / datasets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>e.g. the ethnographic narrative, field notes from the same project in a different season, related data like photographs</i>
Data level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the file: the data type ('field notes'), the file format, etc. • Information about the file content: what do abbreviations and codes in the field notes mean?

Table 1: Field notes metadata and documentation overview. 'CV' indicates that the use of a controlled vocabulary is preferable (i.e. a standard list). This table cannot be exhaustive, since each research project and set of field notes differs. When deciding on which metadata and documentation to include in your case, consider what information is needed to understand the field notes.

12 For more archaeological and cultural heritage controlled vocabulary terms, see <https://termennetwerk.netwerkdigitaalergoed.nl/en>.

13 For more social sciences controlled vocabulary terms, see <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/>.

To best understand what to include, it is useful to have a look at examples. You can find some good examples, although not specifically on field notes, in the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (CESSDA, 2017-2022: Section 2). You can also look at how others have done this (e.g. the example in the box 'Example of a dataset including field notes'). Consider if there is enough information for you to understand and use the field notes in the examples, or if you would add anything else.

How to add documentation and metadata?

You can add metadata and more detailed documentation to a dataset in four, not mutually exclusive, ways:

- Using a README file, to be archived/published with the field notes. This is a text file in which you write all documentation for a dataset or part of a dataset, such as the methodology used for collecting the data, a list of all files included, an explanation for each variable / column header in the file. See the Cornell University template for what this could, and should, contain.¹⁴
- Separate, structured documents, for example for a list of all files, a list of abbreviations and codes used (a codebook), to be archived/published with the field notes.
- Directly in the file. Depending on which file format is used, it may be possible to write metadata in the file content or to add metadata to the file properties. For example, simply as added text in a text document, as EXIF metadata for images, or in 'properties' for Word or Excel.
- When publishing your field notes through a research data repository (see section 4.5),

you will have the opportunity to fill out structured metadata fields.

4.3 Digitising field notes

When field notes are not directly made in digital form, they will need to be digitised to be published. Find a balance between increasing the usability of the notes and the time available.

- Scanning the notes as a PDF is the quickest way to digitise notes, but the text may not be very legible, depending on the handwriting and it may be harder to remove personal data.
- Transcribing the notes to a text document takes more time but the text will be legible and easier for another researcher to use.
- Annotating transcribed notes takes the most time but it makes the data more usable by adding additional context and explanations.

For full searchability and context, information from the notes can also be added to an existing overview database, but this takes considerable time (see case study 4).

It is perhaps also useful to consider here that sharing something may be better than nothing: even if someone will have to puzzle over the handwriting later on (and tools are available to help), it may very well still be helpful to have the data available instead of it being lost or inaccessible completely. Future research projects may have their own budgets and new available technologies to help them to process the notes.

¹⁴ You can find the template at <https://data.research.cornell.edu/data-management/sharing/readme/>

It is recommended to use open and commonly used file formats to archive or publish field notes (DANS, 2025). For example, a PDF/A for a scanned document and TXT for text files (full list at DANS, 2025; see also Schmidt and Ernenwein, n.d.).

4.4 Making field notes sharable: Pseudonymising / anonymising

If the notes contain personal information, and depending on what participants agreed on sharing, a certain level of pseudonymisation or anonymisation is normally required.

The difference between these is that pseudonymised notes may be traced back to the individuals with help of a key, while anonymisation is irreversible (see section 3). For example, if all names are replaced by numbers (and other identifying information is also removed), but a separate table is kept somewhere in which these numbers and names are connected, the data would only be pseudonymised. Moreover, a combination of information can lead to identification (e.g. “37 years old”, “lives in Leiden”, “works as a researcher in Mediterranean archaeology”) so the data is also not actually anonymous.

For guidance on how to de-identify, see the resources in section 3. Keep in mind that:

- Removing names is not enough to pseudonymise or anonymise.
- Depending also on the sensitivity of the research, you may want to pseudonymise your field notes from the start, so that if someone else were to see them, they would not immediately be able to identify the participant.
 - For example, in the US, there is not the same protection of research data as in the EU, and your original field

notes may be requested by a judicial court, in which case it may be essential to protect participant identity from the start and only ever use pseudonyms in your notes.

- It is very hard to completely anonymise something, so it is normally required to have informed consent; if the data is fully anonymised, it is no longer considered personal data according to the GDPR and can (legally) be shared.
- Also consider whether the notes will still be useful if they are completely anonymised.

4.5 Where to share them?

Which platform should you choose to share field notes? While other researchers may be able to find a dataset from publications and citations, there are other ways in which you can increase the findability of your dataset. The best place is a ‘trustworthy’ research data repository and to submit the field notes as (part of) a dataset there.

You can find research data repositories at re3data.org.

- Ideally, choose a discipline-specific repository, so that others in your field can easily find the dataset and relevant metadata can easily be added. You can find such a repository by checking where others in your field publish their data, or where you tend to find datasets yourself.
 - Good examples are the DANS Data Stations¹⁵ for Netherlands-based academics, Pangaea¹⁶,

the UK Archaeological Data Service¹⁷, the UKDS¹⁸, Qualiservice¹⁹, and The Language Archive.²⁰

- Otherwise, you can choose an institutional data repository.
 - Several Dutch universities offer DataverseNL instances, such as the Leiden University Dataverse.²¹
- Another option is a generic data repository, like Dryad or Zenodo. (OpenAIRE n.d.; CESSDA Training Team, 2017-2022)

When choosing a repository, you can look out for certifications, like CoreTrustSeal. This indicates that the repository meets certain standards. However, if a repository does not have a certification, it does not automatically mean it is not suitable (or 'trustworthy').

You can use the following criteria to assess if a repository is a good place for your data:

- Is the repository focused on research data?
- Are there (relevant) metadata fields?
- Will your dataset get a persistent identifier, like a DOI?
- Are there licence options?
- Does the repository guarantee long-term preservation?
- Is there data preservation expertise present?
- Is the repository indexed so that your field notes will be findable?

- Are there any costs? This does not reflect on the quality of the repository, but if there are costs involved and you do not have a budget, it may rule out a repository.
- If relevant: does the repository guarantee that restricted-access data will be held securely?

If your organisation has a data management expert or data steward, you can reach out to them to ask for advice about picking a research data repository.

4.6 Multilingual field notes

In some cases, field notes consist of multiple languages.

Here, additional considerations need to be made:

- To start with, clearly indicate in the metadata which languages were used.
- If possible (i.e. if there is time), annotate the notes to indicate which language was used where. You can annotate this manually and/or by using software.
- If possible (i.e. if there is time) and useful, it would be good to have a version where everything is translated into one common language (e.g. English), also retaining the original.

15 <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/data-stations/>

16 <https://www.pangaea.de/>

17 <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/deposit-data/>

18 <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/deposit-data/>

19 <https://www.qualiservice.org/en/>

20 <https://archive.mpi.nl/tla/>

21 <https://dataverse.nl/>; <https://dataverse.nl/dataverse/leidenuniversity>

Case study 1b:

Annotated anthropological field notes shared in two ways

See case study 1a for the full context; based on work by Janneke Verheijen (Verheijen 2013a, b, c; Verheijen in Flohr et al. 2025; Verheijen and Van der Geest 2020).

For her PhD research, Janneke Verheijen collected a large amount of field notes, her primary data.

She found it important to share these and did this in multiple ways:

- The field notes were part of her dissertation, in which segments of field notes were numbered and referred to (with numbers and hyperlinks) in the dissertation's main text. The dissertation with the field notes was shared as a PDF in the dissertation repositories of the two universities Janneke was affiliated to (Verheijen 2013a, b).
- To ensure long-term preservation and findability of the field notes as a dataset, the dissertation was also shared in the DANS repository (Verheijen 2013c).

Case study 4:

Archaeological field notes shared through a database

By Pascal Flohr

For archaeological fieldwork, field notes are, together with photographs and X-Y-Z measurements, the primary data. Often consisting of written text with sketches, they are written mostly in a structured way on field forms with boxes prompting controlled vocabulary entries. In addition, and for smaller

and more ad hoc projects sometimes only, they can still be in the form of simply text 'jottings' and sketches made directly in the field in a paper notebook.

The Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (EAMENA) project aims to collect information on archaeological sites and landscapes and make this available through an open database (eamena.org).

The information on the archaeology is mostly collected through remote sensing imagery, such as freely available satellite images and from the literature, but field visits are also conducted to add information which can only be gathered on the ground. Between 2017 and 2019, I conducted such 'site visits' at various locations in Jordan.

We documented the archaeological information through photographs, GPS coordinates, and field notes. The field notes were done both in structured forms, including controlled vocabulary terms and with space for free text and sketches, as well as free text and sketches in paper notebooks (see Fig. 3b-c). The notes were made directly in the field, and occasionally 'cleaned up' afterwards — i.e. jottings from the notebooks might be put onto the forms to have everything in one place and missing photo numbers were added to the forms too. As time went on, I realised the importance of taking enough time in the field to make sufficiently detailed notes.

The information obtained in the field was added to the highly structured database, with a selection of the photographs. The field notes themselves were all scanned and are preserved on the University of Oxford's server (with all photographs). The idea was to also

add these scans to the database, relating them to the site records. However, as this was time consuming, this work has not been finalised to date. What has been done, was to add any information from the field notes that did not fit into the structured fields, in a free-text box. Rich context information was given for part of the field visits in an open access publication (Flohr and Finlayson, 2021) where for each site the unique EAMENA database number is also given. Although clearly time consuming, in this way the notes were made available within their context.

Several years on, it emerged, however, that while all records were still present in the EAMENA database, it was not very easy to

retrieve them in a search; the photographs were often not visible, and moreover the links between different records (i.e. between photos and archaeological sites) had broken, most likely during a database migration. And while the database's sustainability is guaranteed for a good number of years, once the project ends, possibly in 2027, no one may be available to give access to the field note scans held on the university server alone. The lesson learnt therefore is that for such important primary data as archaeological field notes, the best option is to also submit a static copy to a research data repository — even though the notes have much less context there, at least it helps to preserve and make them available in the long-term.

Taking semi-structured field notes during archaeological survey. Photo: Karak Neolithic Survey / Pascal Flohr.

5. Final thoughts

With this guide, we set out to give practical advice on how to share field notes, and in this way to encourage more people to do so. We took into account legal and ethical considerations, and other reasons for sharing or not sharing field notes. If you have read this guide, it is likely that field notes form an important part of your research data, or of the data you advise researchers on. We hope that the main text and perhaps especially the case studies have inspired you to share your field notes—or encourage their sharing—as openly as possible, for others to read and reuse, so that the notes—and you—get the recognition they deserve.

Additional Resources

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